

SCOPING PAPER

INDUSTRIAL SYMBIOSIS

A NEFI Innovation Hub

NEFI – The Innovation Network for Industrial Transformation

NEFI – New Energy for Industry is an innovation network consisting of over 100 industry partners, 8 research partners, and 4 institutional partners. With 25 research and innovation projects dedicated to industrial transformation in Austria, an investment volume of nearly €100 million has been mobilised.

The goals of NEFI are:

- **Climate Neutrality** – Supplying selected sites with up to 100% renewable energy.
- **Value Creation and Location Security** – Promoting technology development and exports “Made in Austria”.
- **Industrial Resilience** – Ensuring energy supply, optimising processes, and improving infrastructure for Austrian industry.

The solutions developed within NEFI address 53% of the CO₂ emissions expected by 2040 and have the potential to generate an economic benefit of €2.2 billion. Additionally, by 2040, more than 25% of fossil energy imports could be avoided.

Achieving a climate-neutral industry by 2040 requires significant research and development efforts. Essential technologies are not yet fully developed, tested, or scalable to a sufficient extent. To bridge technological gaps and strategically drive innovations along realistic, scenario-based transformation pathways, six Innovation Hubs have been established.

NEFI Innovation Hubs

The NEFI Innovation Hubs are specialised networks led by renowned research institutions. Their goal is to initiate high-impact research and innovation projects that support the transition to a climate-neutral industry and position Austria as a technology leader in renewable energy and industrial innovation.

Both large corporations and small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), as well as research institutions, are invited to participate in the Innovation Hubs.

NEFI Innovation Hubs: value proposition for partners

- ☑ Regular networking and information events: The NEFI Technology Talks present current technologies, trends, and developments.
- ☑ Support throughout the innovation process: From project idea to funding application and impact assessment.
- ☑ Dissemination of results: Effective communication and visibility.
- ☑ Access to state-of-the-art laboratory infrastructure.

The NEFI Innovation Hubs focus on the following key areas: CCUS, Circular Economy, CO₂-neutral Gases & Hydrogen, Electrification & Energy Efficiency, Flexibility, and Industrial Symbiosis. These topics have been identified as crucial for achieving industrial climate goals across different industries and scenarios ([NEFI Pathway to Industrial Decarbonisation](#) and [transform.industry - in German](#)).

1. Industrial Symbiosis – Current developments and trends

A holistic approach to energy and resource efficiency is vital to meet climate targets. This also involves identifying and leveraging synergies between businesses as well as between businesses and urban areas. Concepts such as industrial symbiosis, where resources and energy are shared and utilised efficiently, hold significant potential for promoting climate neutrality.

Key trends in industrial symbiosis are:

- (1) Industrial-Urban Symbiosis (IUS):** IUS is increasingly emerging as a key trend in sustainable urban and industrial development. In this approach, industrial companies and urban areas cooperate by using waste and by-products from one party as resources for the other. Through the targeted exchange of materials and energy, synergies are created that reduce overall consumption and enhance the efficiency of a region. Political and legal frameworks at the European and national levels – such as the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP) and the Waste Management Act (AWG) – are driving this development forward. In Austria, the circular economy strategy reinforces this trend with ambitious targets: reducing the material footprint to 7 tonnes per capita by 2050, lowering domestic material consumption to 14 tonnes per capita per year by 2030, increasing resource productivity by 50%, and raising the circularity rate to 18% by 2030.
- (2) Industrial-Industrial Symbiosis (IIS):** IIS is emerging as a growing trend in industry, with a focus on establishing a network of energy and resource flows between companies. Through the targeted exchange of waste heat, by-products, and materials, efficient circular systems are created that reduce costs, lower environmental impact, and optimise resource use.
- (3) Energy Communities and Resource Networks:** A growing trend in the industry is the emergence of energy communities and resource networks, which require close collaboration between companies, local authorities, and other stakeholders. An effective material and energy exchange requires continuous innovation in infrastructure and technology to enable efficient symbiosis. Political frameworks and tailored incentives play a key role in this development. Cluster and network initiatives at the regional level are driving this trend forward, fostering connections between businesses and regions. Targeted matchmaking in the field of secondary materials and energy helps identify cross-industry industrial symbioses. The integration of digital technologies optimises and accelerates the process of material and energy exchange, further increasing the momentum of industrial symbiosis.
- (4) Exergetic Optimisation and Process Efficiency:** Exergetic optimisation, which is closely linked to improving process efficiency, is gaining importance. While conventional energy efficiency measures focus on reducing overall energy consumption and maximising energy output—often without a detailed consideration of energy quality—exergy analysis also takes into account the quality and usability of the available energy. Optimising processes from an exergetic perspective enables a deeper understanding and more precise control of process efficiency by considering both energy quality and unavoidable losses in real-world systems. As a result, it leads to a more comprehensive and sustainable improvement in energy efficiency.

2. High-Potential Technologies and Innovations in Industrial Symbiosis

Based on the general trends in the field of industrial symbiosis, the following high-potential technologies and innovations can be identified:

- (1) Digital methods for intensifying Industrial-Urban Symbiosis (IUS):** The successful implementation of IUS requires the active involvement of all stakeholders. It is essential to consider the interests of all parties and develop IUS scenarios where the tangible benefits—whether economic, ecological, or societal—are made clear, not only through increasing the degree of symbiosis within a region but also for each individual stakeholder. This complex challenge calls for the development of suitable modeling and optimisation methods. The development of regionally focused IUS scenarios, based on model regions and incorporating quasi-static considerations of energy and material flows, provides valuable insights into the potential of IUS and enables an informed assessment of the ecological, economic, and societal benefits of these approaches.
- (2) Simulation and optimisation methods:** Mathematical models form the foundation for analysing material and energy (exergy) flows between the involved partners, enabling the identification and assessment of network-like interactions at the material, energy, and exergy flow levels. By simulating various scenarios, companies can identify potential risks and challenges early on and take proactive measures. Simulation methods also allow for the prediction of the ecological and economic performance of symbiotic relationships, significantly improving the chances of successful implementation. Optimising symbiotic networks requires the use of specialised mathematical algorithms and the definition of appropriate ecological and economic objectives. This approach helps identify economically optimal solutions while minimising resource consumption.
- (3) Innovative business models for Industrial-Urban Symbiosis (IUS):** The development of innovative business models is, alongside available technologies, a key success factor for the realisation of industrial symbiosis. Optimal symbiosis scenarios will only succeed if they offer not only ecological but also economic benefits for all involved partners. It will be necessary to align individual business models with the economic and strategic orientation of the entire industrial system in order to generate long-term added value through industrial symbiosis.

3. Main Research Questions in the field of Industrial Symbiosis

As part of the NEFI Innovation Hub for Industrial Symbiosis, projects will be developed that focus on the development of **methods to identify and utilise potential for industrial symbiosis**. A key challenge in developing such methods lies in data availability and security. In particular, data exchange between companies without existing business relationships presents a problem, as does ensuring data protection. To overcome these challenges, making participation more appealing to businesses and ensuring data management in compliance with data protection regulations are essential prerequisites. Research questions include:

- Identification of energy-based industrial symbiosis potentials, including circular economy-promoting key technologies
- Identification of the Pareto-optimal balance between the ecological and economic benefits of the symbiosis
- Subsector-specific and technology-oriented identification of industrial symbiosis potentials
- AI-assisted data collection methods

Furthermore, the Innovation Hub will develop projects that focus on the application of **simulation and optimisation methods** to systematically unlock potentials for industrial symbiosis. A central challenge in developing these methods is data availability, data quality, and data security. Research questions include:

- Development of linear or surrogate models for relevant recovery and conversion technologies based on physical models
- Integration of synthetic industrial load and generation profiles (e.g., electrical) and synthetic waste heat profiles
- Development of optimisation algorithms for system optimisation, including cost minimisation and exergetic optimisation
- Forecasting methods to predict demand, supply, and prices
- Exergetic optimisation of process chains, linkages, and cascades
- Investigation of the impacts of climate neutrality technologies on process chains
- Methods for identifying and determining flexibility options in IIS and IUS networks

The NEFI Innovation Hub also focuses on **identifying drivers and removing barriers to establishing industrial symbioses**. A central challenge is the consideration of waste management regulations and compliance with EU taxonomy regulations and ESRS indicators. Close collaboration with authorities and committees is necessary, as well as early involvement of potential investors. Research questions include:

- Identification of relevant legal and economic frameworks to make industrial symbiosis more attractive
- Development of business models for individual stakeholders to implement industrial symbioses

4. Out-of-Scope Topics and Collaborative Overlaps

The following topics and industries are outside the focus area of the Innovation Hub:

- **Detailed Technology Development:** The focus is on integrating key circular economy technologies and alternative process routes through technology descriptions, process parameters, and KPIs for technology evaluation. Central to these developments are input and output data of energy and material flows, matchmaking platforms, business models, and mathematical methods for network simulation and optimisation.

Through cooperation and alignment between the NEFI Innovation Hubs, synergies can be leveraged, technological trends identified, and innovations accelerated.

The NEFI Innovation Hub for Industrial Symbiosis expects overlaps with the following NEFI Innovation Hubs:

- **Circular Economy:** Industrial symbiosis is a tool of the circular economy. The goals, drivers, and barriers to implementing industrial symbioses are closely linked to the principles of the circular economy.
- **Electrification & Energy Efficiency:** Key technologies of industrial symbiosis are based on sustainable energy carriers, including electrical energy. Electrified technologies and the enhancement of energy efficiency are crucial for successfully implementing industrial symbioses.

5. Hub Co-Leads & Contact Persons

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